

MEASURING THE MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PERFORMANCE OF CONFORMAL LOAD-BEARING ANTENNA STRUCTURES UNDER MECHANICAL LOADING

Mitch Dunn¹, Thien Bui¹, Samuel Munro¹, Michael Adams¹, Alice Greenan¹,
Clement Beteille¹ and Martin Veidt¹

¹School of Mechanical & Mining Engineering, The University of Queensland
Brisbane, Australia
Email: m.dunn1@uq.edu.au

Keywords: Smart materials; Hybrid; Laminates; Electrical properties; Mechanical properties.

ABSTRACT

Conformal Load-Bearing Antenna Structures (CLAS) are multifunctional composite materials that integrate structural and radio communication capabilities, offering significant potential for aerospace applications. While these structures are named for their load-bearing capabilities, experimental studies validating their electromechanical performance under mechanical loading remains limited. This paper presents proof-of-concept experimental methodologies for characterising the electrical behaviour of embedded patch antennas within composite laminates subjected to tensile and flexural loads.

To minimize interference from test fixtures, custom setups using low-dielectric polymer components were developed, enabling antennas to radiate primarily into free space. Microstrip-fed rectangular patch antennas were fabricated using glass/epoxy laminates with laser-cut copper foil. Electrical performance was assessed during loading, including return loss, resonant frequency and radiation pattern.

Results show that mechanical strain induces predictable shifts in resonant frequency consistent with theoretical models. Flexural testing confirmed that fixture design and proximity to dielectric and conductive material surfaces influence antenna performance. Realised gain measurements under bending reveal the impact of laminate deformation on antenna radiation pattern.

These findings demonstrate the feasibility of simultaneous mechanical and radio frequency (RF) testing methodologies for assessing CLAS performance and for supporting design workflows that combine simulation and experimental verification. This work contributes to advancing multifunctional composite technologies through rigorous electromechanical characterisation, aiding future integration of conformal load-bearing antenna structures into high-performance aerospace systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conformal load-bearing antenna structures (CLAS) are a class of multifunctional composite structures capable of functioning as antennas for radio communication in addition to their role as load-bearing structural components. Multidisciplinary technology development driven by the CLAS concept over the past few decades has led to many configurations, but patch antennas (and arrays) made by layering thin copper foil into laminated structures are commonly featured and many designs rely on this fundamental building block. Understanding how these elements perform under load is essential to understanding the coupled mechanical-electrical behaviour of these structures, and critical to designing high performing aerospace vehicles.

Literature studies on CLAS have primarily focused on novel methods to manufacture different configurations of antennas and less focus has been paid to electromechanical performance. Some studies have looked at the performance of antennas after a loading or damage event [1], though most are limited to simulation studies [2]. The use of simulations is a natural choice for designers, as commercially available software is necessary to design patch antennas given the interaction between electromagnetic

radiation and surrounding structural material. This study presents methods for collecting experimental antenna performance data of these structures under load to confirm the findings of simulation studies.

The performance of an antenna against its design parameters can be measured in many ways: realised gain, radiation pattern, resonant frequency, bandwidth, impedance, polarisation and more. These measures can range from single values such as centre/resonant frequency, to multi-dimensional functions such as realised gain which is a function of two polar coordinates and frequency.

An additional consideration is that many antenna measurements are in fact measurements of a larger electrical network. Commonly this includes coaxial cables used to carry electrical signals, and connections between elements. In the case of antennas embedded into composite laminates, there is generally a standard radio frequency (RF) connector (such as Type N or SMA [3, 4]) attached to the composite and soldered to the active element or feed network. Electrical measurements of a CLAS are therefore measurements of the antenna, feed network including solder joints, RF connectors and cables.

The breadth of measurable characteristics, complexity of measured data, and the requirement for a whole-of-system approach means that experimental testing requires some thought and care, whether one is seeking to compare different antennas, compare the performance of a loaded CLAS to an unloaded CLAS, or perform quality assurance on as-manufactured CLAS. One final complication is that conductive or dielectric materials near an antenna influence its radiation pattern. Experimentally characterising antenna performance on aircraft such as UAVs is complicated by the influence of nearby aircraft body [5, 6] for example. Measured experimental results for combined mechanical and RF testing are therefore a function of any apparatus used for fixturing and applying load.

This paper describes some proof-of-concept experimental measurements of antenna characteristics that largely focus on the following research questions:

1. Can we modify standard mechanical tests to reduce the influence of test fixtures on measured antenna characteristics?
2. Can we collect antenna performance data of load-bearing antenna structures under load to compare with simulation studies?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows:

- Section 2 outlines the theoretical basis for predicting frequency shifts in microstrip-fed patch antennas under mechanical load.
- Section 3 details the design and fabrication of experimental specimens.
- Section 4 describes the testing methodologies developed to minimise fixture interference during tensile and flexural loading.
- Section 5 presents and analyses the electromechanical performance results.
- Section 6 concludes with key findings and recommendations for future research.

2 MICROSTRIP-FED RECTANGULAR PATCH ANTENNA

Figure 1 shows the typical design of a microstrip-fed rectangular patch antenna on a dielectric substrate with a ground plane. The following geometric parameters of the rectangular patch antenna determine the characteristics of the antenna:

- Length (L): determines frequency of fundamental mode
- Width (W): chosen to maximise radiation efficiency
- Substrate height (h): determined by application
- Relative permittivity (ϵ_r): material property
- Microstrip width (W_0): chosen to match impedance of source; function of h and ϵ_r
- Recess length (y_0): chosen to match impedance of patch

Figure 1: Typical design of a microstrip-fed rectangular patch antenna [7]

Modelling the antenna as a resonant cavity between patch and ground plane [7], the frequency of the fundamental mode, f_{010} , is ultimately a function of patch length, patch width and substrate height (Equation 1); however the influence of patch length is greater than patch width or substrate height.

$$f_{010} = \frac{c}{2L_{eff}\sqrt{\epsilon_{r,eff}}} \quad (1) \quad \epsilon_{r,eff} = f(W, h) \quad (2) \quad L_{eff} = f(L, W, h) \quad (3)$$

Mechanical strain of a conformal load-bearing antenna structure can change the characteristic frequency of the antenna. Since the fundamental mode of a rectangular patch antenna depends strongly on patch length, strain along the length direction of a rectangular patch changes the resonant frequency of the antenna; a positive change of length will decrease the frequency. While many conformal load-bearing antennas are not designed using rectangular patches, any planar antenna undergoing strain will change characteristics in a similar fashion. The rectangular patch is a simple, easy to analyse design for studying general trends and answering our research questions.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SPECIMENS

Figure 2 shows the specimen design used in this work for investigating the effect of tensile loading along the length direction (L) of a microstrip-fed rectangular patch antenna. The Tensile Specimen consists of a fibre-reinforced composite laminate having a laser-cut copper foil patch antenna and microstrip feed on the top side and a copper foil ground plane on the bottom side. These specimens are manufactured using two layers of 8-harness satin weave glass/epoxy prepreg, and the copper foil elements are laid up into the laminate prior to vacuum bag cure in an oven.

Figure 2: Specimen design used to investigate the effect of tensile loading

The microstrip line is terminated by an SMA connector; the pin is soldered to the microstrip, and the ground flange is soldered to the ground plane. Perspex tabs are bonded onto both sides of the specimen at each end. The tabs serve two purposes: to ensure that standard mechanical testing machine grips do not contact the microstrip and to ensure an air gap above the microstrip. If a dielectric material were to sit on the surface of the specimen, over the microstrip, this would change the characteristic impedance of the microstrip and affect antenna performance.

A similar design of specimen is used for flexural testing (Flexural Specimen A in Table 1), however no tabs are bonded to these samples. Flexural Specimen B is an alternative flexural testing specimen design where the total height of the laminate is kept fixed, but the active antenna element is embedded one ply beneath the surface. Since flexural strain is dependent on distance from the neutral axis, the antenna elements in Flexural Specimens A and B experience different levels of strain for the same radius of curvature. The microstrip and patch dimensions are adjusted to take into account the effect of the superstrate ply on effective permittivity and microstrip impedance.

Table 1: Specimen parameters for tensile and flexural testing experiments

Specimen Parameter		Tensile Specimen	Flexural Specimen A	Flexural Specimen B
Patch length, L	[mm]	18.9	30.8	30.3
Patch width, W	[mm]	23.9	39.1	38.3
Substrate height*, h	[mm]	0.55	1.10	0.825
Superstrate height, h^+	[mm]	–	–	0.275
Material	–		E-Glass/epoxy	
Substrate relative permittivity, ϵ_r	–	4.3	4.3	4.3
Microstrip width, W_0	[mm]	0.96	1.90	1.39
Recess length, y_0	[mm]	6.2	10.1	9.9
Specimen length	[mm]	250	210	210
Specimen width	[mm]	30	65	65

*Due to manufacturing variability, the cured substrate height is observed to vary by up to 5% from these nominal values.

Figure 3 shows layup schematics for the two flexural specimens, and for a case where paint is applied as a cosmetic coating to Flexural Specimen A. These schematics are not to scale and are intended to illustrate that the antennas are fabricated by manufacturing a larger composite laminate panel containing multiple antennas, which are later waterjet cut from the panel. While Figure 3 shows two patch antennas per panel, this process scales to higher numbers of antenna per panel.

Figure 3: Layup schematics for (a) Flexural Specimen A, (b) Flexural Specimen B, (c) Flexural Specimen A with paint

The final experimental specimen type produced for this study is a sandwich-structured composite panel; its design form is very similar to the Tensile Specimen and Flexural Specimen A, with the inclusion of a polymethacrylimide (PMI) foam core and an additional face sheet/skin, as shown in Figure

4. Two configurations for this specimen exist; Configuration 1 is designed to undergo flexural strain of the opposite sign to Configuration 2, i.e. tensile vs compression strain.

Figure 4: (a) Layup configurations for the Sandwich Panel test coupons, (b) Ansys HFSS model of Configuration 1

Table 2: Specimen parameters for sandwich panel antennas for flexural testing

Specimen Parameter		Sandwich Panel
Patch length, L	[mm]	10.1
Patch width, W	[mm]	13
Substrate height, h	[mm]	0.275
Substrate material	–	E-Glass/Epoxy
Core material	–	PMI foam (3mm)
Substrate relative permittivity, ϵ_r	–	4.3
Microstrip width, W_0	[mm]	0.54
Recess length, y_0	[mm]	3.4
Specimen length	[mm]	350
Specimen width	[mm]	50

4 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGIES

Figure 5 shows the experimental test setup for tensile testing; a tensile testing machine is used to load specimens in tension while a Vector Network Analyser (VNA) is used to measure return loss, S_{11} (Equation 4). The specimens are loaded to 2% nominal strain, which is calculated by crosshead displacement. Periodically during the tests, at increments of 0.25% nominal strain, each sample is analysed using the VNA and S_{11} measured. A video extensometer is also used to measure the average strain over the length of the patch. From each S_{11} curve, the resonant frequency (minimum in return loss) value is recorded so that a change in frequency can be observed as a function of applied strain.

Figure 5: Experimental test setup for tensile testing

$$S_{11}(dB) = 10 \log \left(\frac{\text{Reflected Power}}{\text{Incident Power}} \right) \quad (4)$$

For flexural testing, multiple experimental setup concepts have been developed and trialled. Traditional four-point bending test fixtures for universal test machines are made of steel, including the loading pins. The close proximity of the loading pins to the microstrip, and the proximity of both the four-point bending fixture and the universal test machine to the antenna during testing make conventional flexural testing undesirable for composite laminates with embedded antenna elements. The main goals of the developed experimental setup concepts were to:

1. Replace all test fixture structure with polymer fixtures to reduce influence on antenna.
2. Replace loading pins with polymer pins to reduce influence on microstrip and antenna.
3. Reduce the amount of radiated power that could be reflected back to the antenna, either by:
 - a. Absorbing the radiation, or
 - b. Allowing the antenna to radiate into as much free space as possible.

Figure 6 shows the first of these concepts, a small anechoic box designed to fit to a universal test machine. The chamber is lined with RF absorbing foam, rated to the frequencies of interest of the antennas under test. Four-point bending fixtures have been designed and 3D printed from PLA, and polycarbonate loading pins are used. Figure 6(b) shows Flexural Specimens sitting in the test chamber (without the top loading fixture or top of box present). An access hole allows routing of a coaxial cable for VNA testing of the antenna while under load. Conventional four-point bending testing can be performed on these samples with a slow rate of crosshead displacement and continuous recording of the VNA to yield resonant frequency and bandwidth of the antenna at different strain levels.

Figure 6: Anechoic box concept for flexural testing of multifunctional composite laminates

Figure 7: Test fixture for placing multifunctional composite laminates under flexural strain without external loading.

Figure 7 shows a test fixture that is designed to place multifunctional composite laminates under flexural strain without the use of an external loading device such as a universal test machine. The motivation for this concept is to allow for radiation pattern testing of the antenna while it is under flexural strain. For example, this test fixture can be used in a conventional antenna pattern measurement setup in an anechoic chamber that simulates free space. The test fixture outer pins can move, so that five discrete levels of flexural strain or curvature can be applied to the test specimen. Figure 7(b) shows a painted Flexural Specimen A installed into the test fixture and deformed into the “20mm” position, which is equivalent to 20 mm of crosshead displacement if the anechoic box loading fixture were used in a universal test machine.

A set of experiments was performed to compare four-point bending using the developed anechoic box concept (Figure 6) to four-point bending using the static testing fixture designed to eliminate the need for external loading (Figure 7). Using the universal testing machine and anechoic box fixture, five Flexural Specimen A type samples were loaded such that the patch antenna is put into tensile strain; the patch elongates and theory predicts a drop in resonant frequency. VNA measurements were taken at 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 mm of crosshead displacement. Similarly, three Flexural Specimen A type samples were placed in the static testing fixture at curvatures equivalent to 0, 10 and 20 mm of crosshead displacement. Changes in resonant frequency were calculated for each specimen and the results of this analysis are shown in Section 5.

Finally, a concept has been developed for performing four-point bending in a universal testing machine, utilising low-dielectric polymer supports, where the antenna is allowed to radiate mostly into free space (see Figure 8(a)). The antenna faces straight down into over a metre of free space, under which RF absorbing foam rests on the testing machine structure. Figure 8(b) shows a little more detail including VNA connected to the test specimen during loading. As for the previous concepts, this setup allows for the measurement of S_{11} of the antennas to investigate how resonant frequency shifts with flexural deformation. Specimens are loaded to 30 mm of crosshead displacement, with return loss measurements taken at 5 mm increments of crosshead displacement.

Figure 8: Experimental setup for four-point bending of a Sandwich Panel

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Six Tensile Specimens were manufactured for this work and loaded in tension using the methodology described in Section 4. Figure 9 shows an example of S_{11} curves obtained for a single specimen, at nine levels of crosshead displacement. Figure 10 shows the main result of this testing: the change in frequency for all six specimens is shown (marker average, error bars min and max) along with the change in frequency predicted by basic theory model presented in Section 2. Note in Figure 10, the x-axis is the average strain across the patch measured using video extensometer, ϵ_{patch} , whereas the strain values listed in in Figure 9 are nominal strains calculated from crosshead displacement.

Figure 9: Example of return loss vs frequency data for tensile specimen.

Figure 10: Measured vs. theoretical resonant frequency shift in tensile specimens as a function of strain of patch (measured with video extensometer).

The experimental data for tensile testing agrees somewhat with the predictions of basic theory, which are obtained using Equation 1 with L_{eff} calculated from $L(1 + \epsilon_{patch})$. The relatively narrow spread of results and good linearity of the experimental trend are promising results for this testing concept. The discrepancy between model and experiment of approximately 25-40% is similar to that reported in literature for strain-sensing patch antennas [e.g. 9,10]. We noted during our testing, out-of-plane deformation of the specimens were observed due to the unsymmetrical layout of the composite; copper is much stiffer than the glass/epoxy substrate and one side of the specimen has a ground plane occupying the entire face. This out-of-plane deformation is not captured by the basic model and could easily explain the results; this deformation also makes numerical simulation of the coupled mechanical-electrical problem challenging using commercial software such as Ansys HFSS.

Figure 11: Change in resonant frequency vs crosshead displacement for (a) anechoic box concept, and (b) static test fixture.

Figure 11 shows the main results comparing the anechoic box test setup to the static test fixture. Figure 11(a) shows an initial decrease in resonant frequency for all samples as predicted, but then a steady increase in resonant frequency for all samples as flexural strain increases. On further observation and analysis, the authors have concluded that the frequency increase is likely due to the antenna element moving closer to the bottom of the loading fixture and internal surface of the box as it strains, due to curvature of the part. The stand-off distance between the antenna and absorbing foam not remaining constant during testing is not desirable for fair comparison of experimental data points. Ultimately, the findings of these experiments have led to the abandonment of the anechoic box concept by the authors.

Figure 11(b) shows a general downward trend of resonant frequency for the static test fixture experiments, which is in good agreement with predictions. There is a large spread in the data, which may be attributed to the difficulty of precise and repeatable positioning of the specimen within the current fixture design. This concept does not have an issue with the antenna moving closer to a surface during testing, as the antenna is radiating into free space above the test fixture.

The final four-point bending testing concept was trialed using Sandwich Panel specimens described in Section 3. Figure 12(a) shows a specimen of Configuration 1 in the text fixture; the side of the specimen with an antenna is under tension, and the length of the patch should increase, leading to a decrease in resonant frequency. Specimens of Configuration 2 on the other hand, with an antenna on the back face sheet, and are placed under compression in this setup, and this should lead to an increase in the resonant frequency. The results in Figure 12(b) confirm these trends, with the two configurations seeing a frequency trend of approximately equal magnitude but opposite sign. These results represent a successful proof-of-concept of using low-dielectric polymer material for a conventional four-point bending experimental apparatus while ensuring the antenna is radiating into mostly free space.

Figure 12: (a) Sandwich Panel specimen (Configuration 1) bending under load, (b) change in frequency vs. flexural strain for Sandwich Panel specimens (Configurations 1 and 2).

Based on the success of the static test fixture in simple tests for resonant frequency, some preliminary experiments were performed to measure the radiation pattern of specimens under different levels of curvature. Near-field measurements were acquired in an *MVG Starlab* system and processed to approximate far-field gain. Figure 13 shows Flexural Specimen A (painted) in the static test fixture, secured to the central plinth of the *Starlab* system. Realised gain was calculated relative to a standard gain antenna, for frequencies between 2.0 and 3.0 GHz, in 101 steps of 10 MHz, for a 3D field in steps of 3 degrees for azimuth and 3 degrees for elevation. This was repeated for each specimen in the undeformed (0 mm) and deformed (20 mm equivalent crosshead displacement) cases.

Figure 13: Flexural Specimen A (painted) in the static test fixture, secured to the central plinth of the MVG Starlab system.

Figure 14 shows the maximum realised gain at each frequency between 2.0 and 3.0 GHz for Flexural Specimens A and B, each in the undeformed and deformed state. This shows peak realised gain occurs at 2.41 GHz in all tests.

Figure 14: Maximum realised gain vs. Frequency for (a) Flexural Specimen A, painted and (b) Flexural Specimen B.

The antenna radiation patterns at 2.41 GHz are shown in Figure 15 (E-plane) and Figure 16 (H-plane). The E-plane results show that the main lobe of both undeformed specimens has a flat top, separated into two peaks. Flexural deformation of the structures produces a protrusion of this lobe directly away from the patch. The H-plane intersects with this protrusion, and the H-plane results show a consistent increase in gain under deformation.

The effect of laminate curvature on radiation pattern appears identical in form and magnitude between specimen types. This is despite the patch antenna undergoing a different strain magnitude; the patch in Flexural Specimen B is closer to the neutral axis of bending and therefore will experience a lower degree of in-plane strain due to bending. It can therefore be concluded that the change in radiation pattern is attributed to the deformation, i.e. the change of shape, and not a strain effect. Similar results have been shown for wearable antennas, where there is change of shape but no substrate strain [e.g. 11].

These results represent a successful proof-of-concept of using a static test fixture made from low-dielectric polymer material for the measurement of radiation patterns of conformal load-bearing antenna structures under flexural loads.

Figure 15: E-plane radiation patterns at 2.41 GHz for (a) Flexural Specimen A, and (b) Flexural Specimen B

Figure 16: H-plane radiation patterns at 2.41 GHz for (a) Flexural Specimen A, and (b) Flexural Specimen B

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes successful proof-of-concept experimental work to reduce the influence of test fixtures on measured electrical characteristics of conformal load-bearing antenna structures. The developed experimental setup concepts focus on using low-dielectric polymer materials for test fixtures and redesigning experiments such that antennas propagate mostly into free space.

Methods for performing conventional tensile and flexural testing of multifunctional composite laminates have been demonstrated that allow for simultaneous performance characterisation of embedded antennas. The observed trends in data collected during these proof-of-concept experiments tend to agree with predictions made using basic theory of rectangular patch antennas. A methodology that allows conformal load-bearing antenna structures to be fixed under flexural strain while radiation pattern measurements are made has been successfully demonstrated.

This work is an important step towards developing design workflows that include verifying the results of coupled mechanical-electrical numerical simulations with experimental data. For complicated structures, experimental testing is not a feasible pathway toward designing conformal load-bearing antenna structures that perform as expected in real-world applications, and numerical simulations must fill this gap. Experimental work of the type described in this paper can be used to verify and validate simple simulation cases to increase confidence in the results of the design workflow.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper includes work that was supported by the Australian Government Department of Education through Australia's Economic Accelerator Program. This paper includes work that was supported by DMTC Limited (Australia). The authors have prepared this paper in accordance with the intellectual property rights granted by a DMTC Project Agreement.

The authors gratefully acknowledge Kelvin Nicholson from the Defence Science and Technology Group (DSTG) for their contributions to this research and access to radiation pattern measurement facilities through DMTC Project 3.196.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Lu, J. Healey, and P. Callus, "Experimental investigation of electromechanical performance of CLAS under tensile and fatigue loading," *Composite Structures*, vol. 320, p. 117845, 2025. doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2025.117845.
- [2] J. Healey, Y. Lu, and P. Callus, "Mechanical loading effects on conformal load-bearing antenna structures: Simulation of tensile, biaxial, and twisting configurations," *Defence Science and Technology Group, Australia*, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.115123.
- [3] K. J. Nicholson, T. C. Baum, J. E. Patniotis, and K. Ghorbani, "Discrete Holographic Antenna Embedded in a Structural Composite Laminate," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 358–362, Feb. 2020. doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2019.2962902.
- [4] T. C. Baum, R. W. Ziolkowski, K. Ghorbani, and K. J. Nicholson, "Embroidered active microwave composite preimpregnated electronics - pregtronics," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 3175–3186, Oct. 2016.
- [5] N. C. Matson, J. Camp and D. Rajan, "Effect of Antenna Orientation and UAV Position on UAV Communications in 3D Space," *2022 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2022, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/LATINCOM56090.2022.10000517.
- [6] M. Badi, J. Wensowitch, D. Rajan and J. Camp, "Experimentally Analyzing Diverse Antenna Placements and Orientations for UAV Communications," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 14989-15004, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2020.3031872.
- [7] C. A. Balanis, *Antenna Theory: Analysis and Design*, 4th ed. Wiley, 2016.
- [8] B. Mekimah, A. Messai, and A. Belhedri, "Analysis of the effect of dielectric losses on the bandwidth of microstrip patch antenna in stacked geometry and modelling," *SN Applied Sciences*, vol. 2, Article 767, 2020. doi: 10.1007/s42452-020-2292-4.
- [9] J. Wang, Y. Hao, and C. Parini, "Strain measurement using microstrip patch antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 2508–2513, Jun. 2016. doi: 10.1109/TAP.2016.2547381
- [10] D. Tata, S. K. Sharma, and L. Shafai, "Patch antennas for strain sensing applications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 610–617, Mar. 2009. doi: 10.1109/TAP.2009.2014574
- [11] I. Adam, M. R. Kamarudin, A. H. Rambe, N. Haris, H. A. Rahim, W. Z. A. W. Muhamad, A. M. Ismail, M. Jusoh, M. N. M. Yasin, "Investigation on Wearable Antenna under Different Bending Conditions for Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) Applications," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, 2021, 5563528, 9 pages, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5563528>